

Effect of basis for fertilizer application rate on yield, yield attributes, and profit in rice.^a

	State recommendation schedule	Soil test recommendation	Farmers' practice	LSD at 5%
Rough rice yield (t/ha)	6.7	7.2	5.0	0.2
Increase in yield (t/ha) over farmers' practice	1.7	2.2	–	
Expenditure on fertilizers (\$/ha)	96.25	67.90	47.50	
Increase in fertilizer expenditure over farmers' practice (\$/ha)	48.75	20.40	–	
Yield price (\$/ha)	939.40	1008.00	701.40	
Net profit (\$/ha)	550.20	647.15	360.95	
Increase in profit over farmers' practice (\$/ha)	189.25	286.20	–	
Increase in profit over state fertilizer schedule (\$/ha)	–	96.95	–	
Yield attributes				
Plant ht (cm)	111.0	107.7	105.9	3.8
1000-grain wt (g)	20.7	21.8	19.2	ns
Number of tillers	8.1	8.4	6.9	0.9

^aPrice (\$/kg); N, 0.38; P, 0.51; K, 0.19; Zn, 0.27; paddy, 0.14. Expenditure on all agricultural operations (\$/ha) = 292.95.

6 wk after transplanting. The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with three replications.

Soil test fertilizer recommendation resulted in significantly higher economic yields (see table). State fertilizer schedule resulted in significantly higher yields over farmers' practice. □

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Source and time of phosphate application in irrigated rice

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We studied the effect of basal and split application of phosphate through single superphosphate (6.9% P), diammonium phosphate (18-20.0), and ammonium polyphosphate (12-25.2-0) on irrigated rice in 1987 wet season, in a randomized block design with 4 replications.

Soil was sandy loam with pH 6.2, 0.47% organic C, CEC 5.2 meq/ 100 g soil, 9 kg Olsen's P/ ha, 0.15 meq exchangeable K/ 100 g soil, and 1.5 ppm available Zn (DTPA extractable). Daya (125 d) was transplanted 27 Jul with 80-33.3 kg NK/ha. Diammonium phosphate and ammonium polyphosphate at 80 kg N/ha were applied in 50-25-25 splits. Phosphate was mixed with double the weight of soil, wet to less than field capacity, and broadcast over 5 cm water in the field.

Significantly higher yields were obtained with 26 kg P/ ha, irrespective of source and time of application (see table). Highest yield (4.82 t/ ha) was with split application of ammonium

Effect of source and time of phosphate application on yield and yield response, Bhubaneswar, India, 1987.

Source ^a	Rate (kg P/ha) and time of application		Grain yield (t/ha)	Panicles (no./m ²)	Panicle wt (g)	Yield response (kg grain/kg p)
	Basal	Tillering (21 d)				
Control	0	0	2.7	170	1.33	–
DAP	13	0	3.0	213	1.61	22.3
DAP	26	0	3.6	270	1.86	37.3
DAP	6.5	6.5	3.2	228	1.67	41.5
DAP	13	13	3.9	282	1.85	48.4
SSP	13	0	3.2	222	1.54	41.5
SSP	26	0	3.7	275	1.65	39.6
SSP	6.5	6.5	3.1	226	1.61	33.8
SSP	13	13	3.7	268	1.80	37.7
APP	13	0	3.6	251	2.01	53.8
APP	26	0	4.3	303	2.02	63.4
APP	6.5	6.5	3.8	277	2.03	84.6
APP	13	13	4.8	308	2.19	82.3
LSD (0.05)			0.4	24	0.15	–

^aDAP = diammonium phosphate, SSP = single superphosphate, APP = ammonium polyphosphate.

polyphosphate at 26 kg P/ha. Grain yields in general were low because of continuous rain, coupled with strong wind at flowering.

Panicle number/m² and panicle weight were highest on split application of 26 kg P/ha as ammonium polyphosphate. □

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